

Research on the Nanocomposites: Structural and Functional Design

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Three-dimensional Nano Composites

IMPROVE

FUNCTIONALITY:

Thermal conductivity, Electrical conductivity and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Properties

Aerospace Instrumentation

Electronic Packaging

Automotive Engine

Heat Pipes

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Three-dimensional Nano Composites

Melamine sponge

- ✓ Three-dimensional mesh structure with uniform pores
- ✓ Excellent compression performance
- ✓ Strong absorption capacity
- ✓ Excellent processability

As **template material** to form 3D graphene foam

Preparation Method

Three-dimensional Nano Composites

Choose the best carbonization temperature

Fire resistance performance

Macro compression performance

Cyclic compression performance

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Three-dimensional Nano Composites

The SEM images of Carbon foam

The SEM images of Carbon foam coated with graphene

The Changes in the carbon structure

Resin-to-foam immersion

Three-dimensional Nano Composites

The SEM images of the composites

Thermal conductivity enhancement efficiency

Electrical conductivity

Thermal conductivity

Three-dimensional Nano Composites

The contrast of thermal conductivity enhancement efficiency

Sample	Fill loading(Vol%)	TC(W/m·K)	TC enhancement(%)	η	Year
GNP/SBR	24.0	0.48	182	7.58	2013[50]
GNP/PPS	29.3	4.41	1905	65.02	2014[51]
GNS/Epoxy	1.0	0.41	141	141	2014[52]
GNS/Epoxy	2.0	0.32	69	34.5	2015[53]
Graphene/Polymer	25	12.4	6100	244	2015[20]
GNP/Epoxy	5.6	1.8	718	128.21	2016[54]
3D GF/PMMA	0.23	0.27	50	217.39	2018[3]
GNP/HPDE	17.6	~4.13	~404	~22.95	2018[41]
CF800_0.5RGO	0.14	0.47	62	446.54	This work
CF800_5RGO	1.4	0.92	217	156.12	This work

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10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.01.032

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Three-dimensional Nano Composites

Preparation Method

The SEM images of Carbon foam coated with Co_3O_4

The XRD of Carbon foam coated with Co_3O_4

Three-dimensional Nano Composites

The RL of RGO/MDCF

The RL of Co_3O_4 /RGO/MDCF

-31.88 dB

Preparation Method

ILSS

DMTA

The SEM images of SEM images of the representative morphologies of fracture surfaces

1. Effect of graphene oxide addition on the interlaminar shear property of carbon fiber - reinforced epoxy composites

Preparation Method

Microbond Test

TEM of epoxy with graphene

2. Mechanical and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Properties of Carbon Fiber/Graphene Nanosheets/Epoxy Composite

POLYMER COMPOSITES-2015

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ILSS of GNSs/epoxy/CF composites

IFSS of microbond specimen

SE of GNSs/epoxy/CF composites

2. Mechanical and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Properties of Carbon Fiber/Graphene Nanosheets/Epoxy Composite

POLYMER COMPOSITES-2015

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Study on Properties of Graphene/Resin Matrix Composites

AFM images of GO and fGO-1.0

Fracture toughness (K_{IC})

Schematic of the crack propagation modes

Representative SEM images of crack propagating along particle/matrix interface and through fractured particle in epoxy resins

3. Improved fracture toughness of epoxy resin reinforced with polyamide 6/graphene oxide nanocomposites prepared via in situ polymerization

Composites Science and Technology-2019

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Preparation Method

The galvanostatic charge–discharge curves

1. Self-assembled $\text{Co}_9\text{S}_8/\text{RGO-CNT}$ interconnected architecture as composite electrode for supercapacitors

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RSC Advance-2017

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Nano from Our Group

✓ Application of nano materials in the energy field

Synthesis procedure

Cyclic voltammograms

Nyquist plots of the LFP-G-C, LFP-G and LFP-C composite electrodes.

2. Mild solution synthesis of graphene loaded with LiFePO₄-C nanoplatelets for high performance lithium ion batteries

New J. Chem.-2014

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Scheme of preparation of Fe₃O₄/MWCNT/GF

The RL of MWCNT/graphene foam

3. Octahedron Fe₃O₄ particles supported on 3D MWCNT/graphene foam: In-situ method and application as a comprehensive microwave absorption material

Applied Surface Science-2017

Acknowledgment

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Thanks for listening

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